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ROLE OF VARIOUS NATURAL AND SYNTHETIC POLYMERS IN DEVELOPMENT AND IN-VITRO CHARACTERIZATION OF ORAL CONTROLLED DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM OF FEXOFENADINE

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the present work was to formulate and to characterize controlled release matrix tablets of Fexofenadine in order to improve bioavailability and to minimize the frequency of administration and increase the patient compliance. A matrix tablets was developed that releases Fexofenadine over a 12-hour period and the influence of the polymer type and concentration on the release rate of the drug was evaluated. Fexofenadine tablets were prepared by direct compression technique by the use of different natural, synthetic polymers such as gum acacia, hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose K15, xanthum gum and guar gum individually and also in combination. Studies were carried out to study the influence of type of polymer on drug release rate, and *in vitro* release kinetics were examined. All the formulations were subjected to physicochemical characterization such as weight variation, hardness, thickness, friability, drug content. *In vitro* dissolution studies were carried out simulated gastric fluid (pH 1.2) for first 2 h and followed by simulated intestinal fluid (pH 6.8) up to 12 h, and obtained dissolution data were fitted to *in vitro* release kinetic equations in order to know the order of kinetics and mechanism of drug release. Formulated tablets were found to be within acceptable limits for physical and chemical parameters. Formulation containing HPMC K15 obtained the desired drug release profile up to 1h followed zero order kinetics. The release kinetics of the HPMC k15 formulation showed the best linearity ($r^2 = 0.947$) in fitting zero-order kinetics, suggesting the release rate was time independent release. Based on the results, fexofenadine controlled release matrix tablets prepared by utilizing HPMC k15 can attain the desired drug release up to 12 h. Which results in maintaining steady state concentration and improving bioavailability.

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INTRODUCTION

The sustained release dosage form as one that allows a reduction in dosing frequency from that necessitated by a conventional dosage form, such as solution or an immediate release dosage form. An ideal Controlled drug delivery system is the one, which delivers the drugs at a predetermined rate, locally or systematically, for a specific period of time. Oral drug delivery continues to rise in popularity as formulation scientists look for ways to control drug release and improve patient convenience^[1]. The development of controlled release drug delivery system has long been a major area of research in the pharmaceutical industry. Controlled release drug delivery designs involve the application of physical and polymer chemistry to dosage form design to produce well-characterized and reproducible units that control drug delivery into the body within the specification of the required drug delivery profile. Fexofenadine, α, α -Dimethyl - 4 - [1- hydroxy - 4 - [4 - (hydroxydiphenyl-methyl)-1piperidinyl]butyl]- benzene acetic acid is the active carboxylic acid metabolite of terfenadine, and is a non-sedating selective histamine H1 receptor antagonist. Unlike its precursor, fexofenadine lacks the cardiotoxic potential, since it does not block the potassium channel involved in repolarization of cardiac cells. Fexofenadine is effective in the management of allergic rhinitis and chronic idiopathic urticaria. It is taken by mouth twice a daily with food. The pharmacokinetics of Fexofenadine hydrochloride has been studied. It is completely absorbed from the gastro-intestinal tract following oral administration, but bioavailability is reported to be only about 45% due to hepatic first pass metabolism. Most of the drug is eliminated in liver as metabolites and only 1% of the intact drug is excreted from the kidney. Therefore, Fexofenadine hydrochloride might be designed as a suitable delivery system with long term effect^[2,3]. Besides, Fexofenadine may improve a safer alternative in the treatment of asthma and atopic dermatitis and is rapidly absorbed with a long duration of action, making it suitable for once daily administration as its half life is about 14 hrs. Hydrophilic polymers are widely used in the formulation of modified release dosage forms because of their flexibility to obtain a desirable drug release profile, cost-effectiveness and broad regulatory acceptance. HPMC is the first choice for formulation of hydrophilic matrix system, providing a robust mechanism, choice of viscosity grades, nonionic nature, consistent reproducible release profiles, cost-effectiveness^[4].

The use of hydrophilic matrices alone for extending the drug release for highly water soluble drugs is restricted due to the rapid diffusion of dissolved drug through the hydrophilic gel network. Hence in the present work, an attempt has been made to formulate the controlled release matrix tablets of Fexofenadine and investigated for controlled drug delivery using hydrophilic (HPMC K15 and gum acacia) and hydrophobic (MCC) matrix substances in order to control the Fexofenadine release up to 12 h, which results in improved bioavailability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIALS

Fexofenadine was obtained as a gift sample from Aurobindo Pharma Ltd., Hyderabad. Xanthum gum, gum acacia, HPMC K15, and MCC were procured from commercial sources. All other reagents and chemicals used were of analytical grade.

METHODS

Determination OF UV Absorption maxima:

Fexofenadine solution was prepared in 0.1 N HCL and diluted suitably. The UV spectrum of the solution was taken on Lab India 3200 UV/Vis double beam spectrophotometer. The Solution exhibited UV maxima at 298nm. The procedure was repeated with pH 6.8 phosphate buffer.

Preparation of Standard Curve of Fexofenadine :

100 mg of Fexofenadine was accurately weighed and dissolved in little amount of Methanol and make up the final volume up to 100 ml with 0.1 N HCl (pH 1.2) to prepare stock solution. The 10 ml of stock solution was further diluted with 0.1 N HCl (pH 1.2) in 100ml to get 100 μ g/ml (working standard). Then 0.2,0.4,0.6,0.8, and 1 ml of working standard was taken in 10 ml standard volumetric flask and made up the volume with 0.1N HCl to prepare 2 μ g,4 μ g,6 μ g,8 μ g, and 10 μ g drug per ml solution. Then the absorbance was measured in a UV spectrophotometer at 298 nm against 0.1 N Hcl (pH 1.2) as blank. The absorbance so obtained was tabulated as in Table 1. Calibration curve was constructed and shown in Fig.1. The procedure was repeated with pH 6.8 phosphate buffer and absorbance's were measured at 299 nm. The absorbances and standard graph were mentioned in Table2 and figure 2 respectively.

Drug-Excipient compatibility studies:

Fourier Transform Infra Red (FTIR) spectroscopy:

The physical properties of the physical mixture were compared with those of plain drug. Samples was mixed thoroughly with 100mg potassium bromide IR powder and compacted under vacuum at a pressure of about 12 psi for 3 minutes. The resultant disc was mounted in a suitable holder in Perkin Elmer IR spectrophotometer and the IR spectrum was recorded from 3500 cm to 500 cm. The resultant spectrum was compared for any spectrum change

Preparation of Fexofenadine Controlled release Tablet:

Fexofenadine tablets were prepared according to the formula given in Table 1. A total number of 12 formulations were prepared by direct compression method. All the ingredients, including drug, were weighed accurately and passed through 60 mesh sieve separately and collected. The ingredients were weighed and mixed in a geometrical order. The active ingredient and disintegrating agents were weighed and mixed in a small portion of both each time and screen the damp mass into granules and allowed to kept side for drying the blended powder. After the powder dried, allowed to pass through a screen of smaller size. A dry lubricant is added to the powder by blending with the powder. It reduces the friction between the tablet and the walls of the die cavity. Last step in which the tablet is fed into the die cavity and compressed between a lower and an upper punch. 10 mm size punches were used for punching tablets. The tablets were packed in aluminum foil and stored at room temperature.

Table 1. Formulation of Fexofenadine Controlled release tablets.

INGREDIENT	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
Fexofenadine	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60
HPMC K15M	30	60	90	120	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Xanthan Gum	-	-	-	-	30	60	90	120	-	-	-	-
Guar gum	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	30	60	90	-
Talc	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Magnesium.Ste										5	5	5
arate	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5			
MCC pH102	Q.S											
Tablet Weight	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250

Evaluation Parameters (Pre-Compression Parameters)

Micromeritic properties

Before compression, the powder blend of all formulations were subjected to precompression parameters such as angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, Carr's index and Hausner's ratio [5].

Angle of Repose

The flow characteristics are measured by angle of repose. Improper flow of powder is due to frictional forces between the particles. These frictional forces are measured by angle of repose. Angle of repose is defined as the maximum angle possible between the surface of a pile of the powder and the horizontal plane.

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} (h/r)$$

Where,

θ is the angle of repose

h is the height in cm r is the radius in cm.

The powder mixture was allowed to flow through the funnel fixed to a stand at definite height. The angle of repose was then calculated by measuring the height and radius of the heap of the powder formed.

Bulk Density

Bulk density (Db) It is the ratio of the total mass of powder to the bulk volume of powder. It was measured by pouring the weighed powder into a measuring cylinder, and the volume was noted. It is expressed in g/ml and is given by,

$$Db = M / V_0$$

Where, M is the mass of powder, V₀ is the bulk volume of the powder

Both loose bulk Density and tapped bulk density were determined, whereby a quantity (3g) of granules from each formula, previously lightly shaken to break any agglomerates cylinder. After the initial volume was observed, the cylinder was allowed to full under its own weight onto a have surface from the height of 2.5cm at 2-Second intervals. The tapping was continued until no further change in the volume was noted LBD and TBD were calculated using the following formulas

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LBD} &= \text{Weight of the powder} / \text{volume of the packing.} \\ \text{TBD} &= \text{weight of the powder} / \text{tapped volume of the packing.} \end{aligned}$$

Tapped Density (DT) :

It is the ratio of the total mass of powder to the tapped volume of powder. The tapped volume was measured by tapping the powder to constant volume. It is expressed in g/ml and is given by,

$$DT = M / VT$$

Where, M is the mass of powder, VT is the tapped volume of the powder.

Hauser's Ratio

It indicates the flow properties of the powder and it measured by the ratio of TBD to the LBD.

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = Dt/Db$$

Where,

Dt is the tapped density,

Db is the bulk density.

Compressibility Index

The compressibility index has been proposed as an indirect measure of bulk density, size, shape, surface area, moisture content and cohesiveness of materials because all of these can influence the observed compressibility index.

$$\text{Carr's compressibility index (\%)} = [(Dt-Db) \times 100] / Dt$$

Where,

Dt is the tapped density

Db is the bulk density

Drug content uniformity**Standard preparation**

An accurately weighed amount of pure Fexofenadine (100mg) and transferred into 100ml volumetric flask. It was dissolved and made up to volume with phosphatebuffer and absorbance was measured at 220nm.

Sample preparation

An accurately weighed amount of powdered Fexofenadine granules (100mg) was extracted with water and the solution was filtered through 0.45m membrane and absorbance was measured at 220nm after suitable dilution. The amount of Fexofenadine present in granules can be calculated using the formula:

$$At / As \times Sw / 100 \times 100$$

At = Absorbance of sample preparation

As = Absorbance of standard preparation

Sw = Weight of Fexofenadine working standard (mg)

Post compression studies Fexofenadine matrix tablets**Thickness measurement:**

Randomly twenty tablets were taken from each formulation and their thickness was measured using a digital screw gauge. The individual tablet was placed between two anvils of the screw gauge and sliding knob was rotated until the tablet was tightly fitted. The digital reading displayed was noted.

Hardness Test:

The hardness of a tablet is indicative of its tensile strength and is measured in terms of load/pressure required to crush it when placed on its edge. A number of handy hardness testers such as Monsanto or Pfizer type are currently in use, and it is expressed in Kg/cm². The hardness is a function of physical properties of granules like their hardness and deformation under load, binders and above all the compressional force. The hardness has an influence on disintegration and dissolution times and is such a factor that may affect bioavailabilities. For each formulation, the hardness of 5 tablets was determined using a Monsanto hardness tester.

Friability Test:

The friability of the tablet was determined using Roche Friabilator' consist of a circular plastic chamber, divided into 2-3 compartments. It is expressed in percentage (%). 10 tablets were initially weighed (Winitial) and transferred into the Friabilator. The Friabilator was operated at 25 rpm for 4 min. The tablets were weighed again (W final). The percentage friability was then calculated.

$$F = 100 (1-W_o/W_t)$$

Where,

W_o = weight of tablets before friability test

W_t = weight of tablets after friability test

Weight variation Test:

The weight variation test is carried out in order to ensure uniformity in the weight of tablets in a batch. The total weight of 20 tablets from each formulation was determined and the average was calculated. The individual weights of the tablets were also determined accurately and the weight variation was calculated. Indian pharmacopeia limit for weight variation in case of tablets weighing more than 150 mg is $\pm 7.5\%$.

Thickness:

The thickness of the tablets was measured by screw gauge. It is expressed in mm.

Assay of the Tablets:

Ten tablets were randomly selected, weighed and finely powdered; powder equivalent to one tablet was added to 100ml of distilled water in a conical flask. Conical flask was placed on a rotary shaker over-night. And the solution was filtered through a 0.45 μ filter. Absorbance of the resulted solution was measured using U.V Visible spectro photometer against distilled water as blank at a wave length of 256nm. Concentrations were calculated with the help of standard graph and total amount present in the formulation was calculated.

Stability studies:

The selected optimized formulations were subjected to accelerated stability testing, tablets were packed in amber colored bottles, which were tightly plugged with cotton and capped. They were then stored at 40°C/75% RH for 3 months and evaluated for their physical appearance, drug content and drug excipient compatibility at specified intervals of time. The stability of optimized formulation 12 was investigated as per ICH guidelines. The formulation was stored at a temperature 40 \pm 2°C and 75 \pm 5% RH for 3 months

Application of Release Rate Kinetics to Dissolution Data:

Various models were tested for explaining the kinetics of drug release. To analyze the mechanism of the drug release rate kinetics of the dosage form, the obtained data were fitted into zero-order, first order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer-Peppas release model.

Invitro Dissolution studies:

The release of Fexofenadine from the controlled release tablet was studied in 900 ml of 0.1 N HCl in USP dissolution apparatus by using paddle method for about 2 hours. After 2 hours the dissolution medium was withdrawn keeping the tablet in the dissolution basket. Then pH 6.8 phosphate buffer was added to the dissolution medium (900ml) using a USP dissolution paddle assembly at 50rpm and 37.0 \pm 0.5o C. An aliquot (1 ml) was withdrawn at specific time intervals, filtered and diluted to 10 ml with phosphate buffer pH 6.8, and drug content was determined by UVvisible spectrophotometer at 256nm. An equal volume of fresh dissolution medium was replaced to maintain the dissolution volume. Dissolution studies were for a period of 12 hrs and the mean value were taken. Cumulative percentage of drug release was calculated using an equation obtained from a standard curve. The results were displayed in table 5.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**FTIR Spectroscopy results:**

Physical mixture of drug and polymer was characterized by FTIR spectral analysis for any physical as well as chemical alteration of the drug characteristics. The IR spectrum did not show presence of any additional peaks for new functional groups indicating no chemical interaction between Fexofenadine HCl and the used excipients. The observed peaks along with assignment of functional groups to the peak are in table 8. From the results, it was concluded that there was no interference in the functional groups as the principle peaks of the Fexofenadine were found to be unaltered in the spectra of the drug-polymer physical mixture.

Fig.1 FTIR spectrum of pure drug.

Standard graph in phosphate buffer (pH 1.2) :

Standard graph of Fexofenadine was plotted as per the procedure in experimental method and its linearity is shown in table 2 and fig.4. The standard graph of Fexofenadine showed good linearity with R2 of 0.9985, which indicates that it obeys “Beer-Lamberts” law.

S.No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance (at 256nm)
1	2	0.19
2	4	0.34
3	6	0.46
4	8	0.58
5	10	0.71
Correlation coefficient= 0.9985, $y=0.063x+0.0751$		

Standard graph of Fexofenadine was plotted as per the procedure in experimental method and its linearity is shown in Table 2 and Fig. 2.

The standard graph of Fexofenadine showed good linearity with R2 of 0.9972, which indicates that it obeys “Beer-Lamberts” law. It was found that the estimation of Fexofenadine by UV spectrophotometric method at λ_{max} 256 nm in 0.1N Hydrochloric acid had good reproducibility and this method was used in the study. The correlation coefficient for the standard curve was found to be closer to 1, at the concentration range, 2-10 µg/ml. The regression equation generated was $y = 0.063x+0.0751$.

Standard graph in phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) :

Table 3: Concentration and absorbance obtained for calibration curve of Fexofenadine in 0.1 N hydrochloric acid buffer (pH 6.8).

S.No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance (at 256nm)
1	2	0.19
2	4	0.33
3	6	0.45
4	8	0.55
5	10	0.68
Correlation coefficient= 0.9982, $y=0.0595x+0.083$		

It was found that the estimation of Fexofenadine by UV spectrophotometric method at in pH 6.8 Phosphate buffer. had good reproducibility and this method was used in the study. The correlation coefficient for the standard curve was found to be closer to 1, at the concentration range, 2-10µg/ml. The regression equation generated was $y = 0.0595x + 0.083$.

Fig. 3: Standard graph of Fexofenadine in pH 6.8 Phosphate buffer.

Pre-compression parameters:

Tablet powder blend was subjected to various pre-formulation parameters. The angle of repose values indicates that the powder blend has good flow properties. The bulk density of all the formulations was found to be in the range of 0.45 to 0.42 (gm/cm³) showing that the powder has good flow properties. The tapped density of all the formulations was found to be in the range of 0.55 to 0.51 showing the powder has good flow properties. The compressibility index of all the formulations was found to be ranging from 18.18 to 18.24 (Carr's index). Which shows that the powder has good flow properties. All the formulations has shown the hausner's ratio ranging between 1.22 to 1.20 indicating the powder has good flow properties.

Table4. Preformulation parameters of powder blend.

Formulations	Angle of Repose (o) ± SD	Bulk Density (gm/cm ³) ± SD	Tapped Density (gm/cm ³) ± SD	Carr's Index (%) ± SD	Hausner's Ratio ± SD
F1	21.13 ± 0.16	0.459 ± 0.2	0.556 ± 0.67	18.18 ± 1.5	1.22 ± 0.2
F2	19.68 ± 0.15	0.477 ± 0.6	0.559 ± 0.77	14.54 ± 0.12	1.17 ± 0.069
F3	18.26 ± 0.27	0.592 ± 0.3	0.587 ± 0.68	13.79 ± 0.7	1.16 ± 0.054
F4	13.21 ± 0.17	0.469 ± 0.7	0.554 ± 0.62	16.36 ± 0.18	1.19 ± 0.043
F5	21.28 ± 0.14	0.596 ± 0.2	0.589 ± 0.79	13.79 ± 0.4	1.16 ± 0.058
F6	22.13 ± 0.12	0.479 ± 0.7	0.552 ± 0.55	14.54 ± 0.18	1.17 ± 0.053
F7	18.28 ± 0.13	0.598 ± 0.91	0.581 ± 0.68	13.79 ± 0.6	1.16 ± 0.065
F8	14.24 ± 0.18	0.497 ± 0.3	0.576 ± 0.63	18.15 ± 1.8	1.21 ± 0.2
F9	18.56 ± 0.21	0.489 ± 0.82	0.590 ± 0.72	18.12 ± 1.6	1.21 ± 0.2
F10	21.56 ± 0.11	0.490 ± 0.12	0.578 ± 0.75	18.24 ± 1.4	1.20 ± 0.4
F11	21.80 ± 0.19	0.489 ± 0.1	0.569 ± 0.64	18.12 ± 1.3	1.21 ± 0.1
F12	19.23 ± 0.12	0.478 ± 0.14	0.547 ± 0.34	18.11 ± 1.6	1.22 ± 0.2

All the values are expressed as mean ± SD, n=3. SD: Standard deviation.

Quality Control Parameters For tablets:

Tablet quality control tests such as weight variation, hardness, and friability, thickness, and drug release studies in different media were performed on the compression tablet. This indicates the powder blends are good for direct compression. It was observed from (Table 5) that the prepared tablets were evaluated for Weight variation, Hardness, Friability, Thickness, Drug content. Thickness was found to be in the range of 5.5 to 5.5 mm. Hardness of the tablets was in the range of 4.5 to 4.4 kg/cm² which was sufficient for the handling of tablets throughout the shelf life. Percentage % friability was between 0.43 – 0.42 % and complies with pharmacopeial limit of less than 1%. Drug content of Fexofenadine found to be in the range of 97.23 to 98.6, was within the limits as per I.P and ICH guidelines.

Table 5. Post Compression parameters for tablets.

Time(Hrs)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
0.5	5.68	6.54	7.23	4.71	6.32	8.29	2.34	4.79	4.09	11.81	19.89	14.21
1	12.45	14.56	10.45	13.54	11.56	13.65	9.31	11.71	10.53	22.02	28.04	18.87
2	20.46	21.67	21.78	21.56	25.75	19.78	15.67	21.65	32.53	31.70	35.43	27.19
3	32.65	34.62	27.76	29.87	37.74	28.18	22.78	38.76	45.71	39.32	41.65	35.66
4	48.71	48.43	38.76	39.1	49.54	38.89	34.76	49.71	52.56	49.25	47.18	43.32
5	56.62	58.92	45.87	44.98	56.27	48.67	43.78	57.41	63.43	55.28	53.81	51.06
6	69.35	63.43	55.63	56.92	66.75	59.91	55.76	65.81	72.31	60.92	58.89	57.13
7	77.51	77.13	69.43	68.77	79.63	69.41	62.87	72.76	76.31	66.08	64.53	63.63
8	81.54	81.34	76.56	73.65	82.75	76.98	75.61	77.61	81.67	70.44	69.43	69.71
9	83.45	83.76	82.56	78.56	84.17	81.65	81.76	82.45	85.91	77.22	72.83	73.34
10	86.59	85.98	88.67	82.19	89.32	85.71	89.94	85.52	87.31	80.90	79.98	79.27
11	88.82	88.42	93.46	85.35	91.85	89.75	88.83	88.65	88.86	87.83	83.52	82.86
12	90.13	92.18	98.56	90.12	92.89	92.57	92.75	90.53	89.97	91.90	88.65	85.97

Table 6: In vitro dissolution data.

Formulations	Weight variation(mg)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Thickness (mm)	Friability(%)	Drug Content (%)
F1	244±0.71	4.5±0.15	5.5±0.06	0.43±0.85	97.23±1.89
F2	254±0.72	4.3±0.12	5.5±0.07	0.34±0.89	95.58±0.80
F3	260±0.76	4.2±0.12	5.5±0.04	0.49±0.87	98.31±1.47
F4	245±0.71	4.2±0.13	5.4±0.03	0.47±0.82	97.33±1.87
F5	252±0.72	4.3±0.12	5.5±0.05	0.49±0.84	99.32±1.37
F6	258±0.73	4.3±0.11	5.5±0.06	0.34±0.81	99.21±0.25
F7	260±0.75	4.4±0.14	5.4±0.07	0.49±0.87	99.05±0.25
F8	244±0.70	4.5±0.17	5.5±0.08	0.34±0.89	97.55±1.14
F9	256±0.72	4.4±0.16	5.5±0.06	0.34±0.90	95.58±1.35
F10	251±0.74	4.4±0.12	5.5±0.07	0.43±0.89	98.32±0.27
F11	252±0.71	4.3±0.14	5.5±0.04	0.54±0.90	99.05±0.28
F12	254±0.72	4.5±0.17	5.5±0.07	0.42±0.86	98.66±1.17

All the values are expressed as mean±SD, n=3. SD: Standard deviation.

In Vitro Drug Release Studies

In vitro drug release studies were conducted in phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and the studies revealed that the release of Fexofenadine from different formulations varies with characteristics and composition of matrix forming polymers as shown in graphs. From the tabular column 5 it was evident that the formulations prepared with HPMC K15M as retarding polymer in low concentrations the polymer was unable to produce the required retarding action to the tablets. Formulations prepared with xanthan gum were revealed that increase in the concentration retards the drug release. Among all formulations F3 formulation was considered as optimized formulation because it released maximum amount of drug in desired period of time. It was shown 98.65% drug release at 12hrs.

Fig.4: Dissolution profile of formulations prepared with HPMC K15

Fig.5: Dissolution profile of formulations prepared with Xanthum Gum.

Fig.6: Dissolution profile of formulations prepared with Guar Gum.

Fig. 7 FTIR spectrum of optimized formula.

Table No.8: FT-IR data interpretation.

S.No.	Formulation	Wave number in formulation (cm-1)	Characteristic wave number range (cm-1)	Bond nature & Bond attributed
1	Pure drug	3282.46	3200-3400	NH Stretching 20 amine
2	HPMC K 15	2798-57	2900-3000	C-H aldehyde stretching
3	Optimized Tablet	1802-15	1600-1800	C=O ketone stretching

Determination of the Release Kinetics:

To analyze the mechanism of drug release from Fexofenadine controlled release matrix tablets, the *in vitro* dissolution data were fitted to various mathematical models like zero order, first order, Higuchi, Korsmeyer-Peppas and the results are shown in table 6. The optimized formulation (F3) followed zero order kinetics ($R^2 = 0.9473$) indicating that the rate of drug release is independent of concentration, best fitted with Korsmeyer — Peppas model ($R^2 = 0.752$) and followed by nonfickian diffusion ($n = 0.765$).

Table 7: Release kinetics data for optimised formulation.

CUMULATIVE (%) RELEASE Q	TIME (T)	ROOT (T)	LOG (%) RELEASE	LOG (T)	LOG (%) REMAIN
0	0	0			2.000
7.23	0.5	0.707	0.859	-0.301	1.967
10.45	1	1.000	1.019	0.000	1.952
21.78	2	1.414	1.338	0.301	1.893
27.76	3	1.732	1.443	0.477	1.859
38.76	4	2.000	1.588	0.602	1.787
45.87	5	2.236	1.662	0.699	1.733
55.63	6	2.449	1.745	0.778	1.647
69.43	7	2.646	1.842	0.845	1.485
69.43	7	2.646	1.842	0.845	1.485
76.56	8	2.828	1.884	0.903	1.370
82.56	9	3.000	1.917	0.954	1.242
88.67	10	3.162	1.948	1.000	1.054
93.46	11	3.317	1.971	1.041	0.816
98.56	12	3.464	1.994	1.079	0.158

Release kinetics data for optimised formulation

Fig.8: Zero order release kinetics.

Fig.9 Higuchi release kinetics.

Fig.10: Kars Mayer Peppas.

Fig.11: First order release kinetics

Accelerated Stability Studies:

Stability of a drug has been defined as the ability of a particular formulation, in a specific container, to remain within its physical, chemical, therapeutic, and toxicological specifications. Formulation (F3) was kept for accelerated stability study at 40°C ± 2°C, and 75% ± 5% RH for 3 month in the modified stability chamber. After a period of 3 month, it was observed that surface was devoid of any change in color or appearance. It was also noted that surface was free of any kind of microbial or fungal growth. No changes in the smoothness of the tablets were noted. The drug content was found to be 98.6% indicates the no significant changes. The same drug release pattern was achieved after 1 month period indicates the stability of formulation. The *in vitro* release profiles were shown in figure 6. The results were shown in table-10.

Table 10.:Stability studies data of formulation (F3).

Parameters	At Initial Day	After Three Months
Hardness(kg/cm ²)	4.2±0.12	4.1±0.12
Thickness (mm)	5.5±0.04	5.5±0.03
Weight Variation (%)	260±0.76	259±0.75
Drug Content	98.31±1.47	98.21±1.2

Fig. 9 Stability study-*In vitro* release profile of formulation (F3).

CONCLUSION

In the present investigation, attempts were made to formulate Fexofenadine controlled release tablets to provide effective drug release for 12 h by selecting Xanthum gum, HPMC K15, guar gum as retarding polymers. Among all the formulations F3 formulation containing HPMC K15 offered much slow release of Fexofenadine compared with other formulations and drug release predominantly followed zero-order kinetics, suggesting that this system has the propable to maintain a constant plasma concentration of Fexofenadine over 12hours, which could reduce the frequency of administration and the occurrence of adverse effects associated with repeated administration of conventional tablets. Moreover research, it is require to investigate whether such a system will follow zero-order kinetics *in vivo*.

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DECLARATION OF INTEREST

The authors report no conflicts of interest. The authors alone are responsible for the content and writing of the paper.

REFERENCES

- Al-Saidan SM, Krishnaiah YS, Patro SS, Satyanaryana V. *In vitro* and *in vivo* evaluation of guar gum matrix tablets for oral controlled release of water-soluble diltiazem hydrochloride. *AAPS Pharm Sci Tech* 2005,6, E14– 21.
- Chivate AA, Poddar SS, Abdul S, Savant G. Evaluation of Sterculia foetida gum as controlled release excipient. *AAPS PharmSciTech* 2008, 9, 197–204.
- Chein YW. Oral drug delivery and delivery systems, 2nd ed. Marcel Dekker, New York, 1992,139.
- Suresh B., Rajendar Kumar M., Ramesh G., YamsaniMadhusudan Rao, 2008. Orodispersible Tablets: An over-view. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutics* 2008, 9, 206-217.
- Int.J.Pharm.Sci.Rev.res.4(2):87-96. Martindale: *The Complete Drug Reference*. 33rd ed. Pharmaceutical Press, London; 2002, 70.
- Shoib MH, Tazeen J, Merchant HA, Yousuf RI. Evaluation of drug release kinetics from ibuprofen matrix tablets using HPMC. *Pak J Pharm Sci* 2006, 19,119–24.
- Higuchi T. Mechanism of sustained-action medication. Theoretical analysis of rate of release of solid drugs dispersed in solid matrices. *J Pharm Sci* 1963, 52,1145–9.
- Korsmeyer R, Gurny R, Peppas N. Machanism of solute release from porous hydrophilic polymers. *Int J Pharm* 1983,15, 25–35.
- Peppas NA. Analysis of Fickian and non-Fickian drug release from polymers. *Pharm Acta Helv* 1985, 60,110–1.
- US Pharmacopieal Convention. I. Rockville; Maryland: USA: 2008. *USP Asian Edition, USP NF*. The Official Compendia of Standard,362– 4.
- Sekar KS, Nagabashanam MV, Sambasiva Rao KR, Bhikshapathi DV. Design, *in vitro* evaluation of Quetiapine fumarate extended release tablets. *Int J Pharm Bio Sci* 2013,4,578–95.

12. Hirani JJ, Rathod DA, Vadalia KR, A review in orally disintegrating tablets. *Tropical J. Pharm* Vol. 8, no. 2, 161-172. Res 2009
13. Patel P, Dhanani C, Kadeval A, Patel M, Patel N, Patel R, A modern approach on fast dissolving tablets. *Int. J. Modern Pharm* vol.1, no.2,1-17. Res. 2012 14.
14. Leon Lachmann , Herbert A , Liberman , Joseph L.Kaing , The theory and practice of Industrial Pharmacy 293-303. 15.
15. Ansel's Pharmaceutical dosage forms & drug delivery systems, eighth edition 227- 260.
16. Sunada H, Bi YX, Yonezawa Y, Danjo K. Preparation, evaluation and optimization of rapidly disintegrating tablets. *Powder Technol* 2002, 122, 188–98.
17. Marais AF, Song M, de Villers MM. Effect Rowe RC, Sheskey PJ, Weeler PJ(ed). Handbook of pharmaceutical excipients. 4th ed., London and Washington DC: *The Pharmaceutical Press* 2003, 125–35.
18. Abdelbary G, Eouani C, Prinderre P, Joachim J, Reynier JP, Piccerelle P. Determination of the In vitro Disintegration Profile of Rapidly Disintegrating Tablets and Correlation with Oral Disintegration. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics* 2004, 292, 29-41.
19. Kumpusiri S, Maneesatid P, The Dissolution procedure: Development and validation, *Pharmacoepial Forum* 2005, 31,5.
20. Abdelbary G, Eouani C, Prinderre P, Joachim J, Reynier JP, Piccerelle P. Determination of the In vitro Disintegration Profile of Rapidly Disintegrating Tablets and Correlation with Oral Disintegration. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics* 2004, 292, 29-41.
21. Korsmeyer R, Gurny R, Peppas N. Machanism of solute release from porous hydrophilic polymers. *Int J Pharm* 1983,15,25–35.

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